

NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen
Energy Communities

WP 6- Dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities

D6.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan

Horizon 2020
European Union funding
for Research & Innovation

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon
2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement
No 101033700

Project Title	NEON -Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities
Deliverable number	D6.1
Deliverable title	Dissemination and communication plan
Author(s):	Sergio Velásquez, Gisela Soley
Responsible Partner:	P13 - COMET
Date:	28.02.2022
Nature	R
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU
Work package number	WP 06 - Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activities
Work package leader	COMET, Spain
Abstract:	One of the goals of NEON is to raise awareness and establish a vibrant community of interest in the project, as well as to sustain exploitable results after the end of the project. Effective dissemination is seen as the basis for the creation of a critical mass that will assure the engagement of a sufficient number of stakeholders serving as champions and early adopters of NEON service concepts. A dissemination and communication plan are defined to create an early network of stakeholders and engage a relevant number of events aiming at providing 'outsider view' of the project to the consortium.
Keyword List:	Communication, dissemination, exploitation

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Horizon 2020 Work Programme (H2020) under grant agreement no 101033700.

This report reflects the views only of the authors and does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible or liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Editor(s):	Sergio Velásquez, Gisela Soley
Contributor(s):	
Reviewer(s):	
Approved by:	
Recommended/mandatory readers:	

Document description

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
V 0.1	08/12/2021	Table of contents	Sergio Velásquez
V 0.2	11/02/2022	First draft version	Sergio Velásquez
V 0.3	04/14/2022	Final version based on ENGIE and R2M review	Cintia Escandell
V 1.0	18/11/2022	Updated version based on ENGIE and R2M review	Cintia Escandell

Executive summary

This deliverable (D6.1) contains NEON's communication and dissemination plan, a guide that describes the actions, tools, and channels to be used throughout the whole project life. The aim of the document is to outline the strategy, activities, and tools that this project will carry out to reach effective and market-oriented communication and dissemination activities to maximize the impact of the project. The purpose is that NEON partners engage in the presentation of the project and its results as they become available at thematic industrial events, workshops, journals and conferences in energy domain and relevant fields.

The communication approach will be incrementally built in three phases. The first covers moderate actions targeting project awareness (web site, social media, brochures, press releases). The second aims to create user groups and trigger the energy domain community. The third ensures that the project results are widely known to all stakeholders.

The document also defines the key performance indicators (KPI) that will be used to assess the effectiveness of dissemination activities.

The plan also describes the timing of the different phases and activities related to communication.

This report initiates a first reporting period consisting of data collection by the consortium partners and will be subject to successive updates and modifications throughout the life of the project according to the monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of the activities, as well as the emergence of results and new information. To ensure the incorporation of new information as it emerges, as well as the results of the project itself, this plan should be reviewed in each reporting period.

On behalf of Authors

COMET Team

Table of Contents

1. Introduction.....	9
1.1. Objectives	9
1.2. Definitions	9
1.3. Audience	10
1.4. Abbreviations/Glossary.....	11
1.5. Contributions of Partners	13
2. Project Background.....	14
2.1. The NEON Project Context	14
2.2. The NEON Motivation and Vision	14
3. Scope and Strategy	15
3.1. Methodology for Communication and Dissemination	16
3.2. Team Organization	17
3.3. Deliverables Related to Dissemination and Communication	19
4. Target Audiences & Objectives	21
4.1. Dissemination Audiences, Channels and Tools	22
5. Communication Planning.....	24
5.1. Messages & Style.....	25
5.2. Channels Tools and Activities	26
5.3. Visual Identity	28
5.3.1. Logo	28
5.3.2. Colour Pallet.....	29
5.3.3. Typographic fonts	29
5.3.4. Internal Templates.....	30
5.4. Website.....	31
5.4.1. Objectives of the website	31
5.4.3. Form to suggest changes to the website	32
5.5. Newsletter	32
5.6. Graphic Materials	33
5.6.1. Poster/Roll-up Banner	33
5.6.2. Brochure	33
5.6.3. Video	33
5.7. Social Media	34
5.8. Press releases	34
5.9. NEON Dissemination Network.....	35
6. Dissemination Planning	36

6.1.	Public Events & Activities	36
6.2.	Workshops.....	38
6.3.	Scientific publications & Events.....	38
6.4.	Dissemination multipliers Networks & Multipliers	39
6.4.1	CUse of the dissemination networks	39
6.4.2	Clustering activities	40
6.5.	Obligations for Communication and Dissemination of Results	42
6.5.1	Dissemination Process	43
6.5.2	Open access.....	44
6.5.3	Communications	45
7.	Time Schedule	46
8.	Monitoring and evaluation	47
9.	Outline for first reporting period & Conclusion	48
10.	Next Steps	50
	References	51
	Internal Review	52
	Internal Review 1	52
	Internal Review 2	54

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. TABLE SUMMARIZING COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND EXPLOITATION DEFINITIONS, OBJECTIVES, FOCUS, TARGET AUDIENCE AND OBLIGATIONS. EXTRACT FROM EUROPEAN IPR HELPDESK DOCUMENT: MAKING THE MOST OF YOUR H2020 PROJECT.....	10
FIGURE 2. STAGED COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY.....	17
FIGURE 3. KEY CONCEPTS FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF THE VISUAL IDENTITY	28
FIGURE 4. NEON LOGO IN DIFFERENT COLOUR VERSIONS	29
FIGURE 5. NEON COLOUR PALLET	29
FIGURE 6. NEON CORPORATE TYPOGRAPHY	30
FIGURE 7. NEON DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE.....	30
FIGURE 8. THE NEON PRESENTATION TEMPLATE	31
FIGURE 9. MEETINGS MINUTES TEMPLATE	31
FIGURE 10. FLOWCHART OF THE WEB CHANGE MANAGEMENT PROCESS	32
FIGURE 11. EVENT REPORT FORM	37
FIGURE 12. FLOWCHART FOR THE DISSEMINATION PROCESS.....	44
FIGURE 13. PLAN FOR THE FIRST YEAR OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES.....	46
FIGURE 14: MONITORING EXCEL.....	48

List of Tables

TABLE 1. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES AND KEY QUESTIONS.....	16
TABLE 2. LEVELS OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITY	16
TABLE 3. KEY CONTACTS IN COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	18
TABLE 4. KEY CONTACTS OF ALL NEON PARTNERS	18
TABLE 5. PROJECT DELIVERABLES TO CONSIDER FOR DISSEMINATION.....	19
TABLE 6. TARGET AUDIENCE CATEGORIES AND DESCRIPTION	21
TABLE 7. AUDIENCES AND MAIN OBJECTIVES.....	22
TABLE 8. DISSEMINATION TARGET AUDIENCES	22
TABLE 9. DISSEMINATION CHANNELS AND ACTIVITIES	23
TABLE 10. COMMUNICATION ELEMENTS AND KEY MESSAGES.....	25
TABLE 11. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS AND ACTIVITIES.....	27
TABLE 12. STAKEHOLDER ITEMS	35
TABLE 13. SCIENTIFIC AND INDUSTRY DISSEMINATION	38
TABLE 14. INITIAL IDENTIFICATION OF DISSEMINATION EVENTS UP TO M18.....	39
TABLE 15. PROJECT TARGETED FOR CLUSTERING ACTIVITIES.....	41
TABLE 16. WP6 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)	47

1. Introduction

This document aims to describe the approach and strategic plan for communication and dissemination of results to maximise the impact of the NEON project. The aim of the document is to outline the strategy, the activities, as well as the channels, tools, and events with which the NEON project will ensure each stakeholder group is adequately informed and engaged. Identifying key exploitable results for each consortium member also paves the way towards future market uptake of NEON's results (D6.4).

This plan also describes the timing of the different phases and activities related to dissemination, and communication. This document will be modified and updated during the development of the project, according to the monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of the communication activities, as well as the emergence of results and new information.

1.1. Objectives

This deliverable helps establish the communication and dissemination strategy to reach the largest number of possible stakeholders, including public, energy users' communities, industry, and academia.

This report is delivered with the aim of:

- Apply communication guidelines from H2020 and to ensure these guidelines are appropriately treated in NEON.
- Establish the framework and fundamental aspects of project communication and dissemination activities.
- Establish the processes to plan, implement, assess, and report dissemination and communication activities across the length of the project in a strategic way.

1.2. Definitions

To avoid misunderstandings, it is always advisable to review the meaning of the three key words in this document: Communication, dissemination, and exploitation. The European Commission has reference terms database from which we extract the following definitions:

What is communication?

It is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

What is Dissemination?

Dissemination means to make the results of a project public (by any appropriate means other than protecting or exploiting them, e.g., scientific publications).

What is Exploitation?

Exploitation is the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating, and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation	
<p>"Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange."</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>	<p>"The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium."</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>	<p>"The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities."</p> <p>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</p>	<p>Definition</p>
<p>Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.</p>	<p>Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research.</p>	<p>Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.</p>	<p>Objective</p>
<p>Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success.</p>	<p>Describe and ensure results available for others to USE → focus on results only!</p>	<p>Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use.)</p>	<p>Focus</p>
<p>Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community incl. media and the broad public.</p>	<p>Audiences that may take an interest in the potential USE of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partner, policymakers).</p>	<p>People/organisations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.</p>	<p>Target Audience</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for Participants • RIA & IA Proposal Template 2.2 b) • Grant Agreement Art. 38.1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for Participants • RIA & IA Proposal template 2.2 a) • Grant Agreement Art. 29 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for Participants • RIA & IA Proposal Template 1.1, 2.1, 2.2 a) • Grant Agreement Art. 28 	<p>Formal Obligations</p>

Figure 1. Table summarizing Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation definitions, objectives, focus, target audience and obligations. Extract from European IPR Helpdesk document: Making the Most of Your H2020 Project

1.3. Audience

The target of this report is twofold: on one side to inform the EU commission, the project officer and the project reviewers about the processes, objectives, performance indicators with respect to Dissemination and Communication activities. On the other side to guide the project partners in the process of making relevant dissemination and communication activities during NEON Project life. The audience is composed among other by:

- NGOs, associations, and other interest groups willing to showcase NEON solutions as best practices.
- Public services wishing to sensitize their communities.
- Citizens principally from EU, with attention paid to children and young adults as future policy influencers.
- Potential future customers for the NEON exploitable results.
- Local/regional EU authorities from EU, e.g., city mayors or economic development agencies.
- General printed/online media representatives (non-scientific, non-industrial), both at regional/national and EU/international level, thus in English but also in the languages of the consortium countries.

1.4. Abbreviations/Glossary

NAME/ABBREVIATION	NAME/DEFINITION
AES	Advanced Encryption Standard.
API	Application Programme Interface.
BMS	Building Management System.
CEC	Citizen Energy Communities.
CEM	Customer Energy Manager.
CDM	Canonical Data Model.
CIM	Common Information Model.
COSMAG	Comprehensive Architecture for Smart Grid.
DLMS	Device Language Message Specification.
DLT	Distributed Commons Protocol.
DSOs	Distribution System Operators.
DR	Demand Response.
ECP	Energy Commons Protocol.
EE	Energy Efficient.
EEBus	Provides the standard for energy networking behind the grid connection and thus enables load and tariff management as the point of transfer to the building.
eIDAs	electronic Identification, Authentication and eTrust Authentication.
EPC	Engineering Procurement and Construction.
ESC	Energy Service Coalition.

ESCOs	Energy Service Companies.
EV	Electric Vehicles.
GDPR	General Data protection Regulation.
GHG	Greenhouse Gas.
ICT	Information and Communications Technologies.
IEC 61131-3	Standard that provides a definition for implementing PLC programming software
IFC OWL	Base the Industry Foundation Classes into Ontology Web Languages.
INFLUXDB	Is the platform for Building and operating time series applications.
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights.
KPI	Key Performance Indicators.
LCOE	Levelized Cost of Energy.
LEC	Local Energy Communities.
MCDA	Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis.
ModBus	Industrial protocol made as way for industrial devices to communicate through just one pair of wires.
MPC	Model Predictive Control.
NIS	Network and Information System Directive.
O&M	Operations and Maintenance.
OGEMA	Open-Source Framework for Energy Management.
Open ADR	Open Automated demand Response.
OWL	Web Ontology Language.
PDCA	Plan, Do, Check, Act
P4P	Pay for Performance.
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller.
PPA	Power Purchase Agreement.
PPC	Pay per Click.
P2G	Power to Gas.

P2P	Peer to Peer.
PV	Photovoltaic.
RES	Renewable Energy Sources.
SAREF	Smart Applications Reference Ontology.
SAREF4ENER	An extension of SAREF with new classes and properties focused on demand response scenarios (energy at home).
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition.
SGAM	Smart Grid Architecture Model.
SOC	State of Charge.
SPINE	Smart Premises Interoperable Neutral Message Exchange.
SWOT analysis	Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities and Threats.
Tick stack	Acronym for a set of open-source technologies or projects from that combine to deliver a platform for easily storing, visualizing, and monitoring time series
TSO	Transmission System Operators.
VESS	Virtual Energy System.
VPP	Virtual Power Plant.

1.5. Contributions of Partners

PARTNER	CONTRIBUTION
COMET	Leads the Communication and Dissemination activities, with the support from all partners. The methodology workshops as well as best practice exchanges will be planned and held by APPA with technical support of all the partners.
R2M	Will coordinate the exploitation strategy and business model specification with the participation of all the partners.
SIF	Will lead the activities towards setting the path to follow-up financing mechanisms
TRAZA	Will support an effective dissemination that will assure the engagement of a sufficient number of stakeholders

	<p>serving as champions and early adopters of NEON. It also will engage in the presentation of the project and its results as they become available at thematic industrial events, workshops, journals and conferences in energy domain and relevant fields.</p>
--	--

Other partners will provide support across WP activities.

Stakeholders (e.g., end-consumers, service providers, policy makers, etc., that are not part of the consortium) that interact with consortium researchers at domain events and workshops will be invited to take part at NEON workshops in the second and third year of the project.

2. Project Background

2.1. The NEON Project Context

While building on results of recently (or soon to be) concluded EU projects, NEON will undertake **coordination and support activities to advance the leveraging technologies and concepts to deliver the next-generation integrated energy services for communities, targeted to enhance the life quality of European citizens, while improving the performance of energy system.** In this endeavour, NEON will exploit building energy efficiency, renewable energy generation and storage, and demand flexibility to increase energy savings, reduce CO₂ emissions, and provide cost savings across sectors. NEON will engage grid stakeholders, service providers and final consumers to establish, in co-creation, the cross-sectoral arrangements and underlying service concepts.

NEON will **join multi-measure energy efficiency interventions and advanced control capabilities to maximize the positive impact of energy efficiency by improving the building operation performance and make the demand-side flexibility as manageable and procurable resource.** NEON will advance the energy efficiency services already available on the market and couple them with other energy services and non-energy benefits, providing an integrated approach to energy generation, storage, and consumption management. To enable servitization of proposed concepts, NEON will bring innovative business and contracting models by integrating EPC with P4P schemes and establish innovative M&V methodology.

The concept of Citizen Energy Communities (CECs), as introduced by Directive (EU) 2019/944, will be leveraged to set the legal and business foundations to enable faster market uptake, and facilitate communities, both residential and non-residential, in becoming energy efficient. The proposed service concepts and business models will be showcased in 4 CEC setups (residential, non-residential, and mixed) serving as early adopters, whereby follow-up replication plans across 7 “follower” communities will be developed during the project.

2.2. The NEON Motivation and Vision

We are all witnesses of increased energy consumption and power grid operation vulnerability as contemporary problems worldwide. The large intermittent power flows from renewables put a strain on the power grid, thus making it more challenging to ensure that electricity supply matches demand. For solving such problems, we are in a need for effective energy service concepts, capable of enabling the

energy efficiency and flexibility resources at the demand side, which is still largely untapped. To fully exploit the energy efficiency concepts already available at the market, and unlock the flexibility potential under demand response services, it is necessary to ensure cutting-edge control capabilities across building systems and energy assets in an integrative manner.

For improved viability of the service offer, it is necessary to enable the cross-sectoral business models that deliver benefits along the energy value chain. The centralised approach traditionally followed in energy systems becomes impractical in this regard, due to lack of scalability, privacy, and capability of dealing with the multi-actor aspect of the problem. This calls for new energy services and business concepts to ensure effective integration of this locked efficiency and flexibility at demand-side into the power system.

While building on results of recently (or soon to be) concluded EU projects, NEON aims to undertake coordination and support activities to advance the leveraging technologies and concepts to deliver the next-generation integrated energy services for communities, either as single or multiple buildings, targeted to enhance the quality of life of European citizens, while improving the performance of energy system at the same time.

3. Scope and Strategy

In line with H2020 guidelines 'Transition to H2020, Communication for EU Projects', the communication strategy aims at defining and adopting specific communication measures and strategies to promote NEON at EU level and beyond aimed to reach a broad range of stakeholders and public.

Main specific objectives are:

- To share and align the knowledge acquired in the initiative with different stakeholders from the energy providers, the users, the energy communities, and the public sector. Whenever possible, a two-way communication approach will be used with stakeholders.
- To disseminate project results to relevant stakeholders and regulatory bodies.
- To promote NEON and its benefits to the European public and contribute to create awareness in the domain of the cross-sectoral business models that deliver benefits along the energy value chain.
- The iterative assessment and improvement of communication and dissemination activities.
- To organise external training programs and workshops for knowledge integration and transfer between energy and user communities within NEON's scope. Particular attention will be given to the activities organised for the pilot sites residents to ensure they become enablers to build the next-generation integrated energy services for communities and take full ownership of NEON results after project ends.

To maximize the Project's impacts, NEON partners have defined an ambitious strategy for Dissemination and Communication, whose structure is provided in this document. The plan will be updated during the project execution and additional information on communication and dissemination will be reported in the periodic reports. It is critical to achieve maximum impact that the efforts under the strategy defined are delivered openly, strategically, and effectively, so that partners have trust and can work closely and seamlessly together, know each-other's strengths and weaknesses, and share a joint learning path.

3.1. Methodology for Communication and Dissemination

The approach to communication and dissemination is based on six groups of activities, related to basic questions that must be answered throughout the course of the project.

Table 1. Communication and dissemination activities and key questions

Activity	Questions	Chapter
Target audience identification	Who are we trying to reach, and why?	4
Communication contents	What are the main messages to be delivered?	5
Communication Tools & Methods	How will we get our main messages across? Which tools should be used for each audience?	5
Dissemination activities	What activities will be performed to disseminate project results? What mechanism for dissemination outside scientific publications will be used?	6
Timing	When should communication actions take place?	7
Evaluation	What was the impact of the communication activities?	8

The methodological approach to communication activities considers three levels, which, although they can be independent in the case of different audiences, can and will also be cumulative when it comes to the same target. The higher the level of communication, the more involved we will be with the target and the more complex and precise the information we manage.

It is noteworthy that the table below is closely related to [Table 7](#) (Audiences and main objectives) and [Figure 2](#) (Staged Dissemination and Communication Strategy) since each communication level is associated with a stage of the project.

Table 2. Levels of communication activity

Category	Purpose
INFORM	<u>Raise Awareness:</u> Raise awareness of the project: its technological plan, product features, objectives, team, tools, and activities. Convey a general understanding of the purpose and benefits of the action.
EXPLAIN	<u>Achieve Understanding:</u> Provide technical and detailed explanations. Answer in detail key questions about the project's activities, methods & tools, phases, and characteristics. Educate and disseminate results.
TRAIN/INTERACT	<u>Early adopter:</u> The NEON's demonstration sites will be our early adopters; this group needs to be trained in the use of NEON tools and methods to become lighthouse examples of the project's goals and reach.
ENGAGE	<u>Stakeholders as Multipliers:</u> Obtain stakeholders' engagement and collaboration. Involve the audience in the project's activities and goals.

Timing the communication and dissemination activities is paramount to achieve maximum reach of NEON’s messages. In doing so, a staged strategy has been conceived, whose progress will be parallel to that of the project development, and that will allow the project to focus its attention firstly in setting-up a strong and far-reaching communication (to inform and explain) and then, once projects results commence to appear, by producing targeting dissemination activities (to ultimately train and engage). Figure 2 shows this approach in time, the purpose of each stage and the tools used to reach the target audiences. To note that once activities start in each stage, they won’t stop until the end of the project, each stage adds more activities to the running ones, except for the identity kit.

The staged approach aligns directly with the activities planned for results exploitation by firstly raising awareness and educating the stakeholder on NEON developments and pilot outcomes (e.g., thus creating a market need) and secondly enforcing the business planning towards actual market uptake (e.g., delivering the solution).

Figure 2. Staged Communication and Dissemination Strategy

3.2. Team Organization

Communication and dissemination activities will be led by the Communication Manager (COM) with the help of all the Consortium as all partners have an important role to play in WP6. A dissemination network, a database of project stakeholders, will be created early in the project and engaged in relevant events aiming at providing ‘outsider view’ of the project to the consortium. NEON will engage in the presentation of the project and its results as they become available at thematic industrial events, workshops, journals and conferences in energy domain and relevant fields, by setting up and maintaining project’s web portal. The portal will operate as a one-stop shop for community of interest and provide access to internal and external resources.

The partners involved in the demonstration sites (4 Citizen Energy Communities as early adopters) should pay particular attention to trying to communicate as effectively as possible in their communities, to adapt the messages to suit their context and to serve as a point of contact with local or national media for both outgoing and non-going communications. It is also important that they respond to inquiries from potential customers and manage contacts and communication with stakeholders.

The following table shows the key people in the communication and dissemination activities:

Table 3. Key contacts in communication and dissemination activities

Role	Person & Contact
Project Coordinator (PC)	Philippe Calvez (ENGIE) philippe.calvez1@engie.com
Project Manager (PM)	Philippe Calvez (ENGIE) philippe.calvez1@engie.com
Technical Leader (TL)	Valentina Janev (IMP) valentina.janev@institutepupin.com
Exploitation and Innovation Manager (EIM)	Raymond Sterling (R2M) raymond.sterling@r2msolution.com
CECs Coordinators (CCC)	Berchidda Municipality (AXPO) Laura Merlo laura.merlo@axpo.com Domaine De La Source (ALB) Michel Meunier michel@albedo-energie.fr Polígono Industrial Las Cabezas (APPA) Lucía Dolera luciadolera@appa.es Stains City (ENGIE) Philippe Calvez philippe.calvez1@engie.com
Communication Team	
Communication Manager (CM)	Cintia Escandell c.escandell@comet.technology
Assistant Comm. Manager	Gisela Soley g.soley@comet.technology

The following table includes the contacts of all NEON partners, who will also be involved in communication and dissemination activities:

Table 4. Key Contacts of all NEON partners

Partner	Contact for Communication Issues	Main Contact
ENGIE	Philippe Calvez	Philippe Calvez philippe.calvez1@engie.com
AXPO	Laura Merlo	Barbara Massa

Partner	Contact for Communication Issues	Main Contact
		barbara.massa@axpo.com
ALBEDO	Michel Meunier	Michel Meunier michel@albedo-energie.fr
R2M	Raymond Sterling	Raymond Sterling raymond.sterling@r2msolution.com
GRA	Simona D'Oca	Alex d'Elia acme@mangrovia.solutions
SIF	Alessandro Asmundo	Alessandro Asmundo asmundo@finanzasostenibile.it
IDAE	Sara de la Serna Fernández	Sara de la Serna Fernández sara.delaserna@idaes.es
APPA	Lucía Dolera	Lucía Dolera luciadolera@appa.es
FOS	Christina Papadimitriou	Venizelos Efthymiou efthymiou.venizelos@ucy.ac.cy
CSEM	Pierre-Jean Alet	Pierre-Jean Alet pierre-jean.alet@csem.ch
IMP	Valentina Janev	Nikola Tomasevic nikola.tomasevic@pupin.rs
TRAZA	Gonzalo Navarrete	Gonzalo Navarrete gonzalo@trazaterritorio.com

3.3. Deliverables Related to Dissemination and Communication

The table below describes the deliverables that feed and structure the exploitation and dissemination effort, setting out its stages and the materials that will gradually be delivered.

The deliverables are shown in the table in chronological order, to better reflect progress, and include many partners. Nevertheless, it is also worth recalling, one more time, that all partners are involved in the dissemination and communication activities, although not all of them are directly responsible for the deliverables.

Table 5. Project Deliverables to consider for dissemination

Del. No.	Deliverable Title	WP	Lead Partner	Type	Dissemination level	Due Date (month)
D1.1	Take-away from related case studies and energy efficiency programmes	1	ENGIE	Report	Public	6
D2.1	Legal and financial framework for cross-service integration	2	SIF	Report	Public	6

Del. No.	Deliverable Title	WP	Lead Partner	Type	Dissemination level	Due Date (month)
D1.2	Service offers co-creation and business planning	1	ENGIE	Report	Public	9
D1.3	Specification of multi-actor interaction across sectors	1	GRA	Report	Public	12
D1.4	Leveraging the power of CECs and consumer perspective	1	IPV	Report	Public	12
D2.2	Multi-actor energy performance contracting	2	ENGIE	Report	Public	12
D2.3	Service financial structure and business risk distribution	2	SIF	Report	Public	15
D2.4	Techno-economic feasibility case study	2	ALB	Other	Public	15
D2.5	Multi-measure interventions and building retrofit planning	2	CSEM	Demo	Public	18
D3.6	NEON ICT platform integration and interoperability	3	IMP	Report	Public	21
D4.1	Open marketplace based on distributed ledgers	4	GRA	Report	Public	21
D3.4	User-tailored services and non-energy benefits	3	FOSS	Report	Public	24
D3.5	Holistic DR service for demand-side flexibility aggregation	3	CSEM	Report	Public	24
D4.2	Performance measurement and verification service	4	ALB	Report	Public	24
D6.6	NEON market analysis	6	R2M	Report	Public	25

Del. No.	Deliverable Title	WP	Lead Partner	Type	Dissemination level	Due Date (month)
D4.3	Remuneration of demand flexibility under P4P mechanisms	4	AXPO	Report	Public	27
D4.4	Automated settlement and service remuneration procedures	4	GRA	Report	Public	27
D5.1	User experience assessment and recommendations	5	COM	Report	Public	28
D5.2	NEON validation analysis and impact assessment	5	ALB	Report	Public	30
D5.4	Legislation framework and adoption barriers	7	IDAE	Report	Public	30
D6.3	Best practices exchange strategy	6	APPA	Report	Public	30

4. Target Audiences & Objectives

This section should identify the audiences we need to reach and define the purposes and will classify each audience into stakeholder groups. Stakeholder groups allow reducing the dispersion as well as allow planning and executing activities that are targeted towards audiences with similar interests.

The next table provides an overview of the different categories that the project will target while the following subsections include more detail on the different target audiences, the purpose of each one and the envisioned channels and communication and dissemination tools to reach them.

Table 6. Target audience categories and description

Category	Description
Direct and intermediate customers	Service providers, technology providers, energy utilities, grid operators (TSO/DSOs), architects and civil engineers, industrials.
Communication nodes and multipliers	Networks, associations, influential nodes, EU circuit.
Media	General media such as TV, radio, or press (local, national, and international) and specialized media.
Related to energy communities	Energy communities, associations of users and providers, cooperatives, municipalities.

Other relevant stakeholders	Government, municipalities, local and regional EU authorities, policy makers (standardization bodies), NGOs, public services, European citizens.
-----------------------------	--

As stated above, NEON will also work with communication lines, depending on the audience we are targeting, the stage we are, and the level of project progress.

Table 7. Audiences and main objectives

Audiences	Objectives	Activity
Public Media Communication nodes and multipliers Other relevant stakeholders	Awareness	INFORM
Stakeholders (in general)	Understanding	EXPLAIN TRAIN/INTERACT
Direct and intermediate customers Related to energy communities	Action, engagement	TRAIN/INTERACT ENGAGE

4.1. Dissemination Audiences, Channels and Tools

All partners will use **synergies in their own networks and target further relevant stakeholders at regional, national, EU and international levels**, in particular main multipliers –i.e., stakeholders capable of highly multiplying the partners’ efforts– and Horizon 2020 projects that could be integrated into the clustering activities. NEON will aim to **make an outreach to educational and research establishments, and relevant stakeholders**. The most outstanding stakeholders are described in the table below.

Table 8. Dissemination target audiences

Target audience	Strategic objective / expectation
Service providers	Many energy providers/ESCOs provide energy services to communities, while demand aggregation is specifically in aggregators’ scope. They are interested in solutions to better manage the energy demand and its associated contracts. NEON contributes to demand-side management, owing to the better use of energy assets, and lower costs of efficiency programs.
Technology providers	Technology providers of building systems, RES and storage, control, and management units, EMS/BMS systems, etc. NEON extends the functionalities of their products and allows effective integration with other vendors’ and energy infrastructure.
Energy utilities (single or multiple energy-carrier)	Energy utilities are one of the channels for commercialization of NEON through collaboration agreements with ESCOs. NEON will be able to integrate (via Open API) data coming from energy utilities and grid stakeholders to increase the exploitation of energy efficiency, renewable energy, demand flexibility and customer satisfaction.

Target audience	Strategic objective / expectation
Grid operators (TSO/DSOs)	The regional and local TSO/DSOs will be interested in NEON solutions for the same reasons as in the case of the energy utilities, while improving the grid stability through exploitation of energy efficiency and flexibility resources.
Government and policy makers	NEON will have an impact on the energy consumption and emissions' reduction. EU governments and policy makers will have a great deal of interest in NEON results to achieve the highly ambitious EU2030 and even 2050 decarbonization goals.
Energy communities and municipalities	As end customers, energy communities (CECs) include many housings, buildings and municipalities, as public entities, which are keen to minimize the normally scarce resources they must allocate and make economic savings in return. They are entitled to follow and apply different regulations to improve the energy efficiency.
Architects and civil engineers	District/building infrastructural architects could be interested in the integration of NEON services in the building planning/design phase. Planners of building efficiency interventions and RES systems will be able to capitalize on NEON.

Table 9. Dissemination channels and activities

	Dissemination channels and activities	KPIs
KNOWLEDGE AND RESULTS TRANSFER	<p>Open access scientific and industrial publications in international peer-reviewed journals: Scientific publications in journals in gold access with Impact Factor or in self-archiving green access with repositories listed in https://zenodo.org/ or provided by consortium members. Potential journals have been identified, considering the most appropriate ones according to the consortium's previous experience: e.g., Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Energy Conversion and Management, Energy Policy, Energy and Buildings, Energy Efficiency, and IEEE Transactions on Smart Grids; as well as Energy Digital, Power Magazine, and Energy Focus for industrial publications. For open access publishing, only journals with impact factor will be considered.</p>	<p>At least 3 scientific & 3 industrial publications in green or gold access</p>
	<p>Participation in exhibitions, scientific conferences, workshops, or industrial events: It is expected that NEON will present the project results at the recognized exhibitions and international conferences including e.g., IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies (ISGT) Europe; ICREN International Conference on Renewable Energy; Electrical Energy Storage (EES); IEEE PES Power Tech; Smart Homes, etc.</p>	<p>Participation in at least 6 events</p>
	<p>NEON dedicated workshops with potential end-users: Whenever possible, experiencing the project first-hand will be the preferred approach with the groups that have been identified as particularly relevant stakeholders for the project. Both participation at workshops/events, and organization of the dedicated NEON workshops, will also ensure the bi-directional flow of communication between the project consortium and the community itself. It is planned to organise at least 2 workshops with local/national stakeholders in NEON CECs countries. The</p>	<p>At least 2 workshops with at least 20 participants each</p>

	Dissemination channels and activities	KPIs
COMMUNITY STRENGTHENING	<p>objectives of these workshops are: (i) Share with different stakeholders the project objectives and results achieved; (ii) Develop business models applicable to the further exploitation of the results; (iii) Define potential supporting measures to extend the use of the project results.</p> <p>NEON main outreach event: NEON will organize the main project exhibition, possibly in the frame of an international scientific, industrial, policy-related, or a similar commercial event, or as a joint activity with related projects. Consortium members, have extensive experience in organizing such events and several success stories. R2M, for instance, has successfully organized the <u>Sustainable Places</u> within the last couple of years, one of the leading conference events in energy domain, with more than 150 people attending on average.</p> <p>Clustering with related H2020 and national projects, and initiatives: to discuss cross-fertilisation and joint activities using synergies, to maximise their impact in common areas, activities, roadmap, and network. NEON will be dedicated to cooperating with related H2020 projects, particularly with InterConnect funded under DTICT-10-2018-2019, going beyond sharing the results. Relations with projects funded under LC-SC3-EE-13-2018-2019 i.e., CSAs SENSEI and AMBIENCE, as well as Ias iBECOME and 24resco, will be established with best practices exchange in mind. Collaboration activities with related initiatives, e.g., Smart Energy Europe (SmartEN), European Federation of Intelligent Energy Efficiency Services (EFIEES) and European Association of Energy Services Companies (eu.esco) associations will be considered. Synergies will be established with sister projects, SmartSPIN and V2Market.</p> <p>Multipliers briefings: at events such as e.g., Smart Grids EU DSO Association and Energy-efficient Buildings, European Utility Week, Smart Homes, CeBIT, ECTP conference. NEON will leverage expert group meetings to organize knowledge exchange and trainings with stakeholders from NEON CECs countries and EU (energy industry, SMEs, academia, etc.). Meetings will be organized with regional and EU stakeholders to present the CECs and deployed platform, and to disseminate acquired knowledge and “know-how”.</p> <p>Thematic meetings will be organized with targeted industry clusters to facilitate cooperation with stakeholders following replication plans.</p>	<p>At least 50 participants</p> <p>At least 1 meeting per year & 1 joint activity</p> <p>At least 3 meetings or presentations at primary events</p>

5. Communication Planning

NEON, aligned with the H2020 guidelines “Transition to H2020, Communication of EU projects”, is developing a comprehensive and creative common communication strategy that includes the development of a common identity and unified messages, the use of traditional and social media, the development of a set of graphic materials and press-release kits and the compilation of a “Dissemination Network” as a contact database, initially from partner’s network, that will help kick-start the dissemination

of NEON. These activities are engrained in the work plan and the following sections will detail the planning, reach and verification means for the delivery these high-impact activities. Some activities are already finished, and some are planned with targeted deliverables and deadlines that will be clearly stated in each section.

5.1. Messages & Style

With the aim of facilitating the transmission of content by all project members, the following key messages are presented here, which, because they are concise and clear, will help to answer the fundamental questions of society and the market, following the basic and current parameters of marketing and communication. These messages are set to be used by all partners for communicating about NEON without the need to require prior approval from the Consortium.

Table 10. Communication elements and key messages

Communication Elements	Key Messages
<p>Context What exactly is NEON?</p>	<p>NEON intends to exploit building energy efficiency, renewable energy generation and storage, and demand flexibility to increase energy savings, reduce CO2 emissions, and provide cost savings across sectors with the concept of Citizen Energy Communities (CECs).</p>
<p>Challenge What is the problem addressed by NEON?</p>	<p>(1) Energy efficiency services for multi-measure building efficiency improvement - Energy Performance Contracting vs Energy Supply Contract (EPC/ESC).</p> <p>(2) Optimal energy asset scheduling (Renewal Energy Systems - RES, storage, and electric vehicle - EV charging) for improved self-sufficiency, Virtual Power Plants vs Virtual Energy Storage-VPP/VES.</p> <p>(3) Advanced building control for optimal operation of heating/cooling systems, lighting, smart appliances, etc.</p> <p>(4) Demand response (DR) services for grid flexibility improvement via explicit and implicit DR mechanisms (Pay for Performance-P4P).</p> <p>(5) Use-tailored services for ensuring comfort, health (air quality, assisted living services) and safety requirements.</p>
<p>Solution How will NEON help solve the problem?</p>	<p>NEON will bring innovative business and contracting models by integrating EPC with P4P schemes and establish innovative M&V methodology. The concept of Citizen Energy Communities (CECs), will be leveraged to set the legal and business foundations to enable faster market uptake, and facilitate communities, both residential and non-residential, in becoming energy efficient.</p>
<p>Differences & Singularities What makes NEON special?</p>	<p>The proposed service concepts and business models will be showcased in 4 CEC setups (residential, non-residential, and mixed) serving as early adopters, whereby follow-up replication plans across 7 “follower” communities will be developed during the project.</p>

Communication Elements	Key Messages
<p>Impact What effects will NEON have?</p>	<p>The main goal will be to report on the overall user experience and satisfaction while interacting with the system (e.g., user acceptance and responsiveness). A focus group questionnaire surveys and interviews with consumers will be carried at each CEC, considering the type of service contracted, their societal aspects, etc.</p> <p>The effect is the overall user engagement as part of CECs, discuss the role of social norm compliance.</p>
<p>Call to Action What can the audience and the stakeholders do?</p>	<p>NEON will engage grid stakeholders, service providers and final consumers to establish, in co-creation, the cross-sectoral arrangements and underlying service concepts. NEON will join multi-measure energy efficiency interventions and advanced control capabilities to maximize the positive impact of energy efficiency by improving the building operation performance and make the demand-side flexibility as manageable and procurable resource.</p>
<p>NEON Summary Paragraph</p>	<p>While building on results of recently (or soon to be) concluded EU projects, NEON will undertake coordination and support activities to advance the leveraging technologies and concepts to deliver the next-generation integrated energy services for communities, targeted to enhance the life quality of European citizens, while improving the performance of energy system.</p>

5.2. Channels Tools and Activities

Communication measures aim to **inform about and promote the project and its results**, conveying research in a non-technical way to **raise awareness among a broader audience about the challenges NEON addresses**.

Besides **helping to reach out the project’s potential end-users and further target audiences (already described) for dissemination and exploitation, the communication activities will also target audiences beyond the project’s own community**, who could be interested in knowing more about the NEON benefits for everyday life. These audiences are:

- NGOs, associations, and other interest groups willing to showcase NEON solutions as best practices.
- Public services wishing to sensitize their communities.
- Citizens principally from EU, with attention paid to children and young adults as future policy influencers.
- Potential future customers for the NEON exploitation results.
- Local/regional EU authorities from EU, e.g., city mayors or economic development agencies.
- General printed/online media representatives (non-scientific, non-industrial), both at regional/national and EU/International level, thus in English but also in the languages of the consortium countries.

NEON will create overall awareness on challenges related to smart energy services, energy efficiency, demand flexibility and RES, as well as regarding the NEON solution in general. CEC visits and user engagement activities will be also undertaken as part of the NEON communication activities. A preliminary list of communication channels and activities can be found in [Table 11](#) and will be periodically updated according to the specific needs of the project and its progress.

Table 11. Communication channels and activities

	Communication channels and activities	KPIs
INFORM AND PROMOTE	Project identity kit with a project branding, poster, templates for internal and external materials and guidelines for partners, e.g., for GDPR compliance.	1 project identity kit
	Project brochure with key project public information, printed in 2.000 copies and updated in the second half of the project with project results (further 2.000 copies).	>2.000 copies distributed
	Online/printed press releases in English at European level , published shortly after project start to raise awareness within the widest audience, the challenges it addresses, its main objectives and partners involved; at project midterm to inform on first achievements and tangible benefits; before the project main outreach event; and at project end or shortly after it to promote project results as providing solutions to fundamental challenges. They will be replicated in languages of the consortium countries at regional/national level, to leverage project coverage by reaching out to non-English speaking audiences.	At least 4 press releases in English, replicated in languages of the consortium
	Public factsheets and electronic newsletters . NEON will start producing the factsheets and newsletters about the project and its scope starting from M12. Further issues will be provided for major results and milestones. Both factsheets and newsletters will be targeted for directly reaching the relevant audiences.	3 factsheets & 5 newsletters >50 subscribers
	Project video . NEON will also discuss the possibility of a joint video with its sister projects financed under the same topic, to increase synergies in both terms of costs and impact. The videos should remain as non-technical and self-explicative as possible to reach the widest audience.	Min. one video having hundreds of views
	Digital info-pack for stakeholders wishing to inform themselves and their communities about the challenges and benefits of smart energy services provided by NEON. It will be mainly based on infographics to reach out to a broader audience and target in particular local/regional authorities by promoting NEON findings.	1 general info-pack produced in M12-M18
INTERACT AND ENGAGE	Public website with a description of the challenges addressed by the project, its consortium, its objectives, and proposed solutions; a cluster section with a list of related projects and major multipliers; a news and events section; a resource section with the project’s public material; a contact form for visitors’ questions; and NEON social media embedded or linked. To stimulate engagement, gamification aspects will be considered, e.g., an interactive quiz with questions linked to energy efficiency and environmental challenges.	More than 100 visits per month At least 1 interactive quiz

Communication channels and activities	KPIs
<p>Social media accounts such as LinkedIn or Twitter, to build up a project community and increase engagement around the various aspects and issues related to Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) becoming more energy sustainable. The project accounts will interact with social media activities of cluster projects.</p>	<p>Social media with at least 500 followers each</p>

5.3. Visual Identity

NEON's visual identity has been built on its main and differentiating technological and management concepts: (1) Service facilitators and investors, (2) ESCOs and DR aggregators, (3) Building owners and occupants and (4) Power utilities and DSOs. In addition, to simplify the visual understanding of the project, three essential concepts have been extracted to reflect these essential dimensions of the project: Renewable Energy/sustainability, energy communities, etc.

The visual identity has been summed up in a brand book that was delivered in month 4 to serve as guideline for the correct use of the visual identity to guarantee its consistency during the project's lifespan. It was made available to all partners on the project repository.

5.3.1. Logo

neon BUILDING NEXT GENERATION INTEGRATED ENERGY SERVICES FOR CITIZEN ENERGY COMMUNITIES

KEY CONCEPTS:

- Multi-Measure Energy Efficiency Building Retrofit Planning · Digital Control for Improved Building Performance · Holistic Optimization Approach to Energy Asset Building · Hybrid Demand Response (DR) Model As Grid Flexibility Enabler · Smart Remuneration Leveraging Distribution Ledger Technology (DTL) · Cross-Sectoral Business and Contract Models

NEON aims to undertake coordination and support activities to advance the leveraging technologies and concepts to deliver the next-generation integrated energy services for communities.

NEON will exploit building energy efficiency, renewable energy generation and storage, and demand flexibility to increase energy savings, reduce CO2 emissions, and provide cost savings across sectors.

NEON will leverage, enable and deliver reliable secure extraction of knowledge from the Energy Communities Digital Ecosystem.

Figure 3. Key concepts for the construction of the visual identity

Figure 4. NEON logo in different colour versions

5.3.2. Colour Pallet

The corporate colour palette works mainly with washed shades of green and blue, and black as secondary. This range of colours allows designing graphics and artworks that are visually attractive and contrasting.

Figure 5. NEON colour pallet

5.3.3. Typographic fonts

The logo has been built with the open-source font *Stick No Bills SemiBold* and the font used for texts is *Urbanist Regular*. For all corporate communications, the *Calibri* family is the recommended font.

FONTS FOR LOGO CONSTRUCTION:

Stick No Bills SemiBold

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234569\$%&/()=?;! "# : ; - @

RECOMMENDED FONT FOR TEXTS:

Urbanist Regular

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
1234569\$%&/()=?;! "# : ; - @

Figure 6. NEON corporate typography

5.3.4. Internal Templates

Two templates have been developed for NEON project using the visual elements explained in previous sections. These templates are to be used by partners when creating NEON documentation and presentations. The two templates are:

- The NEON deliverable template
- The NEON presentation template
- Meetings Minutes template

ACTIVITY REPORT FORM

Title of event / activity: [text]
 Date(s): [dd.mm.yyyy]
 Location: [text]
 URL of the event website: [URL]

• Please indicate if this is one of the following cases by marking with an X:

Organisation of a conference	Website
Organisation of a workshop	Participation to a conference
Press release	Participation to a workshop
Non-scientific & non-peer reviewed	Participation in joint H2020 activities
Exhibition	Participation in another event
Flyers	Communication Campaign
Training	Video / film
Social media	Brokerage event
Trade fair	
Other: [text]	

• Please indicate the type of audience reached, by marking with an X (multiple choices are possible):

Scientific Community	Policy makers
Industry	Medias
Civil Society	Investors
General Public	Customers
Other:	

NEON: Next Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities, has received funding from the European Commission H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101033700

Please indicate the approximate number of people who have attended the event and have been able to get to know the project:
 [Number]

Please let us know the approximate cost in € of organising and/or attending the event:
 [0,00 €]

Agenda of the event / activity:
 [text or image]

Projects and initiatives connected:
 • [Project & brief description]
 • [URL]

Please leave your comments and observations here; your feedback will be of great help:
 [text]

Signatory's contact details:
 [Name and last name], [Company]
 [Telephone]
 [E-mail address]

2

Figure 7. NEON deliverable template

Figure 8. The NEON presentation template

Figure 9. Meetings Minutes template

5.4. Website

The website was planned to be launched in M6 (March 2022). However, a landing page was launched previously by the end of November 2021.

The NEON website was posted at <https://neonproject.eu/> on Monday, February 07, 2022. Deliverable D6.2, with due date M6, details the construction of the webpage with the main elements that conform it.

5.4.1. Objectives of the website

Target of NEON’s website (Deliverable D6.2): wide scale promotion. Link to EU added value on homepage. Reinforced by pointers in social media and press.

5.4.2. Target: more than 100 visits per month; at least 1 interactive quiz.

Before M10, a Publication Schedule will be defined by the Communication Team together with the partners. This Publication Schedule will include a list of articles to be published monthly at the website and social media, specifying authors, dates, and potential topics. These articles will cover general concepts of the NEON project as well as topics closely related with its progress. The aim of this Publication Schedule is to feed the website periodically and strengthen the social networks.

5.4.3. Form to suggest changes to the website

It is expected that NEON’s website will change according to the project development, these changes may refer to design, content, new functionalities, or changes in the CMS (Content Management System) code among others.

It should be noticed that the budget and effort for the website is limited and the needs and subjective impressions from the consortium partners may differ in aspects like the design or the communication style.

Therefore, to properly address these changes a procedure which makes use of a form to suggest changes –and report errors– has been developed. In this way, changes will be properly discussed, budgeted, and planned. This form has been made available as part of deliverable D6.2 due on M6.

Figure 10. Flowchart of the web change management process

5.5. Newsletter

Five newsletters including NEON project progress and outcomes will be created and distributed among the stakeholder community and dissemination network and in relevant events. The newsletter will include a small editorial, news, presentations from NEON members, visual and educational materials on the

progress of the project and its results, past and future events, and links to social networks, among other elements. The full template has been delivered at M6 with D6.2.

Planning: starting in M12, and every 3-4 months.

Target: 5 editions, more than 50 subscribers.

To attract subscribers along the project, we will try to exploit as much as possible the NEON dissemination network and reminders will be posted about the subscription to the newsletter in social media every month.

5.6. Graphic Materials

The NEON public communication kit will consist of a project brand book, project poster and roll-up, a project presentation, brochure, press releases and project videos.

The delivery of these materials, which will substantially support the project at the events is scheduled for month 6 (D6.2) and will be mostly updated when considered necessary by the coordinator and the consortium.

5.6.1. Poster/Roll-up Banner

To give visibility to NEON, a project poster has been designed and adapted to the roll-up format. Widely used for trade fairs, conferences and exhibition material, this display has gained status over the years for being particularly user friendly, with plenty of space to attract attention to the message and increase corporate recognition. In this sense it will be much more adapted to the type of use that the project partners will need to inform and promote the project.

Planning: the delivery of this material is scheduled for M6 with D6.2 (updated when necessary, according to progress).

5.6.2. Brochure

The NEON project will produce a brochure to promote and explain the project and support its dissemination on demonstration sites and the events. The choice of the type of printed material used will be decided based on the purpose, the context of the dissemination and the target audiences. Once designed and upon request, it may also be tailored to fit a particular event or demonstration to better adapt the key messages and impact that wish to be conveyed to the audience.

Planning: the delivery of this material is scheduled for M6 with D6.2 (updated when necessary, according to progress).

5.6.3. Video

One video is planned. We are assessing the possibility of a joint video with NEON's sister projects financed under the same topic, to increase synergies. This video will be posted on the Front Page of the NEON website and distributed through other social media channels for further dissemination.

5.7. Social Media

Part of the engagement to the project will involve all partners actively supporting the communication, including that which takes place on social networks, that way the network can be extended, and the dissemination and communication can be more effectively throughout the project.

To disseminate the project on social networks, NEON will publish content on LinkedIn and Twitter and will be connected to the social networks of partners and stakeholders respectively. The relevance of NEON's presence on Facebook or other identified and useful social media will be assessed.

For this activity, we look forward to the support of all partners.

Planning: these have been set up as part of D6.2 (M6)

5.7.1. LinkedIn

Identification and active contribution in the groups associated and related to the main project's interests, topics, and keywords.

LinkedIn target: 500 group members (tracked "likes").

Metrics: Number of followers and posts.

5.7.2. Twitter

Posts about the content lines detailed before.

Twitter target: 500 followers.

Metrics: Number of followers and posts.

5.7.3. YouTube

The YouTube channel will be created to host the videos that will be performed the project.

5.8. Press releases

The NEON project will prepare a press kit for journalists, which will contain a presentation of the project, press releases, background information and suggested articles. In this way, the media and specialized publications can be contacted with press kits once we have in the database the list of communication contacts.

For dissemination of press releases, we will make available to the partners a form to be filled out and sent to the communication team.

All press releases will be translated to languages of the consortium countries at regional/national level, to leverage project coverage by reaching out non-English speaking audiences.

Target: 4 press releases.

5.9. NEON Dissemination Network

A confidential database will be created and made available to partners on the shared workspace for tracking the development lifecycle of NEON exploitable results and mapping the results to potential market lead and communication channels. Importance is given to connecting those developments with relevant stakeholder groups, events, publications, and news updates that can contribute to market uptake.

The contact base with which to manage the communication, especially of the stakeholders provided by the different partners, will be developed by COM and will require the participation of all partners.

To carry out effective communication and achieve the objectives set out in the project, it will be necessary to request, in this first stage, data on the different stakeholders that each partner will identify within its network. Each partner will be requested to provide at least 10 direct contacts. To avoid any conflict, GDPR rules will be adhered to and in addition, partners will retain “ownership” of the contacts they propose, which means that none of their suggested stakeholder will be contacted without previous explicit consent from the proposing partner.

The data collection phase will be started by the communication manager, who will prepare a form to all partners that must be completed and returned by M9. The categories that partners will be required to complete by M9 are detailed in next table.

Table 12. Stakeholder items

Field	Explanation
#	Numbering
Partner	Partner referring contact and owner of the contact. All initial communications go through this partner
Partner country	Country of the proposing partner
Partner activity	Market activity of the proposing partner
Stakeholder name	Contact Name
Stakeholder surname	Contact Surname
Job title	For addressing purposes
Email	Contact email to receive communication and dissemination material
Country	Contact country for clustering and coverage analysis
Association / organization / institution	Contact organisation
Stakeholder type	Type of stakeholder for clustering: RTO (research and technology organisations including higher education institutions), SME (small or medium enterprise), LE (large enterprise),

Field	Explanation
	GOV (government or public organisations), ASS (association), STD (standardisation and policy makers), MED (Media)
Organizations sector	Relevant sector in which contact develops business for clustering: UTI (utilities), TECH (technology providers), ENG (engineering company), OPE (grid operators) ...
Rationale for inclusion	To enable other partners and deliverable readers to understand the importance of this contact. Also, to identify partners for exploitation-oriented stakeholder engagement phases
Language	If mother language is not English this is helpful to provide more targeted dissemination material
Webpage	Webpage of the organisation
Status	Show the status of the stakeholder: PRO (proposed, engagement needs to start), APP (approved), CON (contacted), ENG (engaged)
Objectives	Objectives of the communication and dissemination activity targeted to this stakeholder
Channels or tools	Suggested means to reach the stakeholder including messages, activities, dates, and materials
Actions carried out	If any further action has been carried out to improve stakeholder engagement
Efficacy and impact of the action	A measurement of the impact of the actions taken to further engage the stakeholders
Feedback from stakeholders	Feedback, if any, of the stakeholders engaged

6. Dissemination Planning

6.1. Public Events & Activities

All partners will perform dissemination activities complying with the procedures on communication spelt out in the Consortium Agreement and considering the guidelines elaborated by the Communication and dissemination plan. Specific actions to be carried out are: (1) Scientific publications, (2) Participation in exhibitions, conferences, workshops, and industrial events, (3) Workshops with potential end-users, (4) Clustering & Community events, (5) Expert groups meetings.

The involvement of the partners in various events is therefore necessary for the successful development of the project's objectives and will involve the following obligations. A process has been set up to notify, manage, track and compile event information for reporting purposes. The process is as follows:

-Prior to the event: The partner(s) should notify the communication team as early as possible of events relevant to the project. They must also inform about the agenda of the event and their intentions, in the case of participating, organizing, etc. If partners need support during the event from the communications

team, they should also notify them in advance and specify what elements they will require. Advance notice will also feed into the overall schedule of project communication, which will help to optimise both the strategy and its impact.

-During the event: It may be useful and usable for the communication team if attendees, participants, or organizers of the event provide information, photos, and contacts during the event. In this way, events can be exploited to create networks, join social networking trends while active and gain audiences.

-After the event: The partners must send the communication team a completed report (see figure below), which will be used for the project documentation to be submitted to the European Commission, and which will also provide very useful feedback for the dissemination and exploitation of the results.

Figure 11 below shows the template form developed by the Communication team to track events.

ACTIVITY REPORT FORM

Title of event / activity: [text]
Date(s): [dd.mm.yyyy]
Location: [text]
URL of the event website: [URL]

• Please indicate if this is one of the following cases by marking with an X:

Organisation of a conference	Website
Organisation of a workshop	Participation to a conference
Press release	Participation to a workshop
Non-scientific & non-peer reviewed	Participation in joint H2020 activities
Exhibition	Participation in another event
Flyers	Communication Campaign
Training	Video / film
Social media	Brokerage event
Trade fair	
Other: [text]	

• Please indicate the type of audience reached, by marking with an X (multiple choices are possible):

Scientific Community	Policy makers
Industry	Medias
Civil Society	Investors
General Public	Customers
Other:	

NEON: Next-Generation Integrated Energy Services for Citizen Energy Communities, has received funding from the European Commission H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101033700

Figure 11. Event report form

6.2. Workshops

Two dedicated NEON workshops and one main outreach event will be organized during the project to open the discussion with relevant stakeholders and disseminate the project results.

The workshops will be planned, hosted, and executed by the partners providing demonstration sites. Each workshop will also involve members of the External Advisory Board. Prior to each workshop, material will be circulated so participants start thinking about the topic and thus enhance the discussions. The objectives of these workshops are:

- (i) Share with different stakeholders the project objectives and results achieved.
- (ii) Develop business models applicable to the further exploitation of the results.
- (iii) Define potential supporting measures to extend the use of the project results.

COM will coordinate the necessary preparation for each workshop including the engagement of local professional organisations for increased dissemination. Outputs from each workshop will be collected by COM and be made available through project’s dissemination channels including project website.

6.3. Scientific publications & Events

NEON pursues and offers excellent science. For appropriate scientific dissemination, the results are expected to be disseminated through the following conferences, exhibitions, journals, associations, and media nodes:

Table 13. Scientific and industry dissemination

SCIENTIFIC JOURNALS AND PUBLICATIONS		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews • Energy Conversion and Management • Energy Policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy and Buildings • Energy Efficiency • IEEE Transactions on Smart Grids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Digital • Power Magazine • Energy Focus
CONFERENCES AND EXHIBITIONS		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies (ISGT) Europe • IEEE PES Power Tech 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICREN International Conference on Renewable Energy • Smart Homes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electrical Energy Storage (EES) • European Smart Grids Summit

The following events, conferences, exhibitions, journals, associations, and media nodes are identified as interesting for the dissemination of NEON. These will be analysed and followed to determine when NEON can and should disseminate to/within them.

Table 14. Initial identification of dissemination events up to M18

Timing	Dissemination Event	State	Rationale/Intent	Lead partners
To be specified	WORKSHOP	Spain	Present the technical development (especially WP3) in relation to the platform and the integration of the cross-cutting services of the energy communities as well as the results of the pilots.	R2M
6-9 Sept. 2022	SUSTAINABLE PLACES 2022	Italy	Overall presentation of the NEON project from the definition of services and the integration of cross-cutting services.	R2M
14-17 March 2023	MIPIM 2023	France	Overall presentation of the NEON project from the definition of services and the integration of cross-cutting services.	R2M
15-16 Nov. 2022	TELFOR 2022	Serbia	Present the NEON services and platform	IMP

The publication of peer-reviewed papers in journals and/or peer-reviewed conference will be in line with the data management plan (open access).

- **Target for scientific publications:** 3 peer reviewed publications in green or gold access
- **Target for industrial publications:** 3 industrial publications
- **Target for event participation:** 6 events (conference participation)
- **Target for main outreach event:** 1 event with at least 50 participants

6.4. Dissemination multipliers Networks & Multipliers

6.4.1 CUse of the dissemination networks

NEON clearly defines an interconnected network of stakeholders: the project partners, the existing network of the partners, other which come from the second and from contacts made during the project.

NEON partners: the consortium members need to be fully engaged and informed of project progress at all stages. They will be the first to evaluate and discuss the results and identify new approaches for dissemination and exploitation. Partners also perform the initial testing and analyse the first set of results. NEON partner organizations have reached marketing campaigns surrounding their products and activities and linked to stakeholder community events. Partner's communication channels are paramount for stakeholder engagement and should be exploited.

Within this group, it is worth highlighting the CECs that are going to carry out the Project pilots. CECs are going to performance the demo activities and will become at the end 'early adopters'; they are the group that will drag the other followers who could gradually join the CECs practices.

NEON partners' existing network: the existing trust between the partners and the networks allows NEON to 'get through the door' with these Stakeholders. That is why we create the Dissemination Network (see Section 5.9). Each partner targets his own network and engages them to become the first advocates of NEON results. This community also serves to brainstorm ideas and provide valuable and timely feedback about project progress and to provide inputs for further Stakeholders and for new markets and incoming market needs that NEON should be aware of.

NEON 'Other actors': this community comes either by reference of the partners or via engagement in the dissemination events or through the dissemination and communication channels. This community needs to be kept engaged and informed since they are the ones that will ensure market uptake after the first advocates demonstrate the benefits of NEON.

6.4.2 Clustering activities

Clustering activities are fundamental for EU research to cross-fertilization of project development and avoid the 'reinventing the wheel' scenario. NEON will take an active role in engaging and leading clustering activities by promoting joint events such as workshops.

NEON will be dedicated to cooperation with related H2020 projects, particularly with InterConnect funded under DTICT-10-2018-2019, going beyond sharing the results. Relations with projects funded under LC-SC3-EE-13-2018-2019 i.e., CSAs SENSEI and AmBIENCE, as well as IAs iBECOME and frESCO, will be established with best practices exchange in mind. Collaboration activities with related initiatives, e.g., Smart Energy Europe (SmartEN), European Federation of Intelligent Energy Efficiency Services (EFIEES) and European Association of Energy Services Companies (eu.esco) associations will be considered.

The [Table 15](#) shows currently open H2020 projects of relevance with respect to the plans and importance of forging collaborations with NEON.

The first listed (SMART EPC, SmartSPIN, V2Market) can be referred to as 'sister' projects, being that they are funded under the same call topic (*LC-SC3-B4E-14-2020 Enabling next-generation of smart energy services valorising energy efficiency and flexibility at demand-side*), while the subsequent projects can be referred to as 'cousin' projects being that they're funded under different call topics but are still of significant interest for NEON.

The “sister” projects are focused on next generation batteries for stationary energy storage, and although they may have a similarity to the objectives of NEON, they still can have cross-cutting issues that can be leveraged such as a focus on stationary energy storage and microgrids issues.

These projects will be analysed and followed within WP6, starting with the most relevant, to determine when NEON can and should disseminate in collaboration with them. The overarching goals are to strengthen the potential impact of the synergistic messages, multiply the audience(s) being reached, and ideally foster efforts towards clustering for dissemination and ultimately results exploitation.

Table 15. Project targeted for clustering activities

Project Title & GA N°	Project Dates & Brief Description	H2020 Details
‘Sister’ Project		
<u>SMART EPC</u> : Next Generation of Energy Performance Contracting (101031639)	From 01/02/2022 to 31/01/2025; Enable the transition of local public authorities towards smart sustainable cities of the future by utilizing existing energy efficiency services as a key for unlocking the potentials of new, emerging technologies and services. By creating advanced and smart concepts for modernization of public lighting in European cities, Smart EPC project will enable large-scale energy efficiency programs while strengthening know-how of regional/national key stakeholders.	Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020 Scheme: CSA Topic: LC-SC3-B4E-14-2020 Proposal: H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2
<u>SmartSPIN</u> : Smart Energy Services to solve the split incentive problem in the commercial rented sector (101033744)	From 01/09/2021 to 31/08/2024; Split incentives present a key challenge to the deployment of energy efficiency measures in buildings. SmartSPIN project will develop a new business model to improve their energy efficiency and flexibility.	Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020 Scheme: CSA Topic: LC-SC3-B4E-14-2020 Proposal: H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2
<u>V2Market</u> : Valorising energy efficiency and flexibility at demand-side using vehicle to grid (V2G) and vehicle to building (101033686)	From 01/09/2021 to 31/08/2024; Incorporating electric vehicle (EV) batteries into the electricity system is essential to promote storage and flexibility capacity. It requires the use of vehicle-to-grid and vehicle-to-building technology combined with energy efficiency and price forecasting ICT tools.	Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020 Scheme: CSA Topic: LC-SC3-B4E-14-2020 Proposal: H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2
‘Cousin’ Project		
<u>TIMEPAC</u> : Towards innovative methods for energy performance	From 01/07/2021 to 30/06/2024; will combine EPC databases with other data sources to make certification more effective and reliable. The methods and tools to enhance the current EPC system will be tested in six EU	Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020

Project Title & GA N°	Project Dates & Brief Description	H2020 Details
assessment and certification of buildings	Member States (Austria, Croatia, Cyprus, Italy, Slovenia, and Spain). The findings will be used to develop training resources about certification processes.	Scheme: CSA Topic: LC-SC3-B4E-4-2020 Proposal: H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2
<u>ARISE</u> : Building an innovative currency of construction skills	From 01/09/2021 to 29/02/2024; will develop a recognition scheme of digital energy efficient Building Information Modelling (BIM) construction skills. An innovative system of universal learner focused stackable micro-credentials for micro module units of learning will be supported by a blockchain-based micro-credentialling system.	Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020 Scheme: CSA Topic: LC-SC3-B4E-2-2020 Proposal: H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2
<u>Smart2B</u> : Smart building management in the clouds	From 01/09/2021 to 31/08/2024; will upgrade the capacity of existing buildings by developing non-intrusive Internet of Things sensors and actuators to control equipment, while improving indoor comfort and energy efficiency. The project will allow for coordinated control of legacy equipment and smart appliances and integrate two existing cloud-based platforms into a single building management platform.	Call: H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020 Scheme: IA Topic: LC-SC3-B4E-3-2020 Proposal: H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2

6.5. Obligations for Communication and Dissemination of Results

This section resumes the processes that have been implemented to guarantee that NEON communication, dissemination and exploitation of results is made according to which is established by our Consortium Agreement, the Grant Agreement and the EC regulations and recommendations, including the General Data Protection Regulation.

Detailed information on these issues could be found in:

- Consortium Agreement, section 8: Results
- Grant Agreement, Section 3 Subsection 3: Rights and Obligations Related to Results
- Data Management Plan (D7.3) - H2020 Programme Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon 2020
- Guidelines on Implementation of Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in projects supported by the European Research Council under Horizon 2020

According to the G.A.:

“Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must —as soon as possible— ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).”

Also, according to article 29.2 for peer-reviewed scientific publications, each beneficiary must **ensure open access** relating to its results.

It should be considered that the open access policies do not change the obligation to **protect results** in Article 27, the **confidentiality obligations** in Article 36, the **security obligations** in Article 37 or the obligations **to protect personal data** in Article 39, all of which still apply.

Ensuring all the above mentioned could be especially complex in some cases, so to ensure the correct dissemination of the results a process —which is also described in the CA— has been implemented.

6.5.1 Dissemination Process

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 29.1 of the Grant Agreement subject to the following provisions.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

The flowchart below resumes the dissemination process:

Figure 12. Flowchart for the dissemination process

6.5.2 Open access

The project will produce datasets related to four demonstration activities in Italy (Berchidda), France (Domaine De La Source and Stains City) and Spain (Polígono Industrial Las Cabezas).

Data management will follow the Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research as established in Article 29.2 of the Model Grant Agreement and Horizon H2020 guidelines.

A dedicated data management plan will be developed in T7.3, integrally taking care that the ethics and the collection of data involving people and organisations will be well thought through and fully comply with GDPR rights involving full consent, adequate secure storage, and withdrawal of data. The process of which will be operationalised by the consortium partners on the project’s collaborative internal portal, based on clear protocols, version control management and updating requirements. Specific aspects of datasets crucial for foreground innovations that require shielding from competitor’s (e.g., costings, detailed financial data) cannot be made accessible publicly for verification and re-use in general due to IP protection measures. Yet, all other data necessary for the verification and reproduction of results as published in scientific journals will be made accessible, following open access standards publishing.

The **strategy for making data openly available** is to ensure Open Access publishing of scientific publications in journals and conference proceedings. Each partner will ensure open access to all peer-

reviewed scientific publications relating to its results and associated datasets. Either as dedicated supplements to journal publications, or as linked data publications tied to journal publications (e.g., Nature Scientific Data, Harvard Dataverse).

All publications and associated data supplements/publications will be self-archived on the public NEON website. Self-archiving (**'green' open access**) means that the published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is deposited in an online repository before, alongside or after its publication but prior the journal editorial staff edits, while **'gold' open access** is related to critical high impact factor journal publications to be made available open access including the editorial staff edits. The deliverables, articles and papers will be published in Zenodo as well.

Thereby data maintenance and preservation will be guaranteed by the consortium partners. Project exploitable results are identified early in the project, and it is already foreseen that partners will protect results via appropriate measures. **To ensure patenting of business methods and software's** is possible, procedures will make clear what information/data cannot be disseminated. Instead, in the event of a decision to disseminate/share the results, data will be generally treated in the following way: results related to data that supports the dissemination, exploitation and future branding of the NEON results will be treated with GREEN or GOLD OA. Instead, results that are related to competitive aspects for the future development and exploitation of the results (e.g., pricing, process, and integration knowledge) will be as RED (restricted).

The project will integrate this in the data management protocols operationalised on the collaborative portal, to ensure partners can when needed update the status for treatment of data for use during and after the project, as detailed in T7.3 (Data Management Plan).

6.5.3 Communications

According to EC guidelines "Communication" refer to those actions where no project results are shared. In this sense, partners should not follow the same process for publishing general information about the project like the one which is typically placed in the "News and Events" section of NEON website.

Partners are committed to align and integrate their communication strategy with the project's one. In this sense, partners are required to make a proper use of social networks¹ and inform the project's communication team at least one week before publishing any press release for its revision –this time restriction could be shortened if the case is justified.

Before making any kind of communication (including short social media communications like tweets), partners should make sure that no sensible information is published. As a first approach, partners are asked to respond to the following questions:

- Are you publishing information that could be protected according to the GDPR?
- Are you using other partner's logo, images, or any other content without asking for his permission?

¹ [soc-med-guide_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

- Are you mentioning other partner without having his approval for publication?
- Are you using any content without being sure that you have the rights to use it?
- Are you publishing information which could be considered confidential –even if it is not directly related to the project results?

If the answer to some of these questions is “yes” or “I don’t know”, the publication could be infringing IPR, GDPR or the CA/GA, so it is not ready to be published. In case of doubts, partners should ask to the communication team to approve the communication. For data management issues, it should be considered that Eneko Olabarrieta from R2M will serve as the NEON data manager. He will interact with partners across the data management life cycle in the project.

7. Time Schedule

As soon as the bulk of the data relating to events, stakeholders and other communication parameters are collected and made available in the database, we will develop an overall communication plan outlining the detailed activities for the four years.

Communication and dissemination activities planned for the first year are as follows:

Figure 13. Plan for the first year of communication activities

8. Monitoring and evaluation

Below is a forecast of the communication and dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). This table may be expanded and reviewed during the project lifespan based on the evolution and needs of the project.

Table 16. WP6 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Key Performance Indicators	Target value	Means of verification
Visits to the NEON website (page views)	3,000 (100 per month)	Analytics monitoring software/Google Analytics
Subscribers to the newsletter	50	Newsletter system dashboard, complying with the new GDPR
Followers of the NEON Twitter account	500	Details on the Twitter account
Members of the NEON LinkedIn group	500	Details on LinkedIn
Press releases	4	Monitoring and reporting by WP6 team and project partners
Scientific publications	3	
Industrial publications	3	
Participation in exhibitions, conferences, events...	6	
Workshops with potential end-users	2 (20 participants each)	
Event organized by NEON	1 (50 participants)	
Clustering events	1 meeting per year + 1 joint activity	
Multipliers briefings	3 meetings or presentation	
Project brochure printed and distributed	2.000 copies	

To maintain a continuous monitoring of NEON coverage on the communication side, an online easy-to-use Excel document will be shared with the partnership to identify relevant events, topics for website news, media appearances, publications, videos, and any kind of external communication material: this tool will

When the information request form will be sent to partners, they will be requested to provide the information below and deliver it to the communication and dissemination team (from month 6 to month 8):

- Stakeholders and contact details.
- Forecast of communication activities.
- Events in which they will participate, or which are relevant to the project.
- Possible local, national, and international media (TV, radio, generic press, magazines) to publish or communicate about the project.
- Specialized journals and scientific publications to disseminate the results.
- Press releases.
- Requests for the communication team.
- Specific contents requested.

As the project progresses, we will be completing the common files and databases, as well as the communication plan, and, in parallel, a systematic review and update of the project and the strategy will be carried out every six months.

10. Next Steps

It will be discussed if the CECs pilots are presented in an open to the public format at the local site. The CECs Pilots are a good communication opportunity and can have a high impact at both project level and locally.

The project counts with pilots: Berchidda Municipality (Italy), Domaine De La Source (France), Polígono Industrial Las Cabezas (Spain) and Stains City (France). As abovementioned, this situation represents an opportunity to carry out far reaching dissemination events around pilots.

Two different approaches will be discussed during NEON to exploit the pilots:

- If the pilots are open, the public, students, and professionals, will know the new innovations, being able to observe operation for educational and professional purposes. In turn, through the WP of communication, information brochures will be provided.
- Consortium meetings could be organised in the pilots. These meetings will be linked with stakeholder workshops and open days for maximising the use of resources and engaged a further range of stakeholders.

References

European Commission Funding & tender opportunities portal (2019, June) EU H2020 Reference Terms.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html

European Commission (2018, April 6). H2020 Programme. Guidance: Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

European IPR Helpdesk (2018, March). Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

<https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E.pdf>

European Commission (2018, December 6). Dissemination of results - Article 29 of H2020 annotated model grant agreement.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf#page=242

European Commission (2018, December 6). Exploitation of results - Article 28 of H2020 annotated model grant agreement.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf#page=240

European Commission (2017, March 21). H2020 Programme. Guidelines to the Rules on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Open Access to Research Data in Horizon 2020.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/oa_pilot/h2020-hi-oa-pilot-guide_en.pdf

European IPR Helpdesk (2015). Factsheet: The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results in Horizon 2020.

https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/FS-Plan-for-the-exploitation-and-dissemination-of-results_1.pdf

European Commission (2015, July). Toolkit for the evaluation of the communication activities.

https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/communication-evaluation-toolkit_en.pdf

European Commission (2015, September). Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants.

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/gm/h2020-guide-comm_en.pdf

Internal Review

Internal Review 1

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes N= no NA = not applicable

Name of reviewer: **XXX**

Organisation: **XXX**

Date: **XXX**

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
FORMAT: Does the document ... ?				
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?				
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?				
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?				
... contain a version table?				
... contain an updated table of contents?				
... contain a list of figures?				
... contain a list of tables?				
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?				
... contain an Executive Summary?				
... contain a Conclusions section?				
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?				
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?				
... use correct spelling and grammar?				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)				
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)				

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy paste text)				
About the content...				
Is the deliverable content correctly written?				
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?				
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?				
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?				
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?				
Are all references in the document included in the references section?				
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (Copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)				

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

X	Document accepted; no changes required.
	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5 (1 = poor, 5= excellent) – using a half point scale. Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5

Internal Review 2

Mark with X the corresponding column:

Y= yes N= no NA = not applicable

Name of reviewer: **Eneko Olabarrieta**

Organisation: **R2M**

Date: **04/04/2022**

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
FORMAT: Does the document ... ?				
...include editors, deliverable name, version number, dissemination level, date, and status?				
... contain a license (in case of public deliverables)?				
... include the names of contributors and reviewers?				
... contain a version table?				
... contain an updated table of contents?				
... contain a list of figures?				
... contain a list of tables?				
... contain a list of terms and abbreviations?				

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
... contain an Executive Summary?				
... contain a Conclusions section?				
... contain a List of References (Bibliography) in the appropriate format?				
... use the fonts and sections defined in the official template?				
... use correct spelling and grammar?				
... conform to length guidelines (50 pages maximum (plus Executive Summary and annexes)				
... conform to guidelines regarding Annexes (inclusion of complementary information)				
... present consistency along the whole document in terms of English quality/style? (to avoid accidental usage of copy paste text)				
About the content...				
Is the deliverable content correctly written?				
Is the overall style of the deliverable correctly organized and presented in a logical order?				
Is the Executive Summary self-contained, following the guidelines and does it include the main conclusions of the document?				
Is the body of the deliverable (technique, methodology results, discussion) well enough explained?				
Are the contents of the document treated with the required depth?				
Does the document need additional sections to be considered complete?				
Are there any sections in the document that should be removed?				
Are all references in the document included in the references section?				

ELEMENT TO REVIEW	Y	N	NA	COMMENTS
Have you noticed any text in the document not well referenced? (Copy and paste of text/picture without including the reference in the reference list)				

SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENTS

PAGE	SECTION	SUGGESTED IMPROVEMENT

CONCLUSION

Mark with X the corresponding line.

X	Document accepted; no changes required.
	Document accepted; changes required.
	Document not accepted; it must be reviewed after changes are implemented.

Please rank this document globally on a scale of 1-5 (1 = poor, 5= excellent) – using a half point scale. Mark with X the corresponding grade.

Document grade	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5